

It may be pointed out that equation (5) may also be written as follows :

$$N\left(\frac{4}{3}\pi H^3\right) = hV_w - \phi_v \quad \dots (6)$$

The symbols N , H , h , V_w and ϕ_v in equation (6) have the same significance as stated already.

It follows from equation (6) that the binding of water molecules by the ions is accompanied by contraction in volume of the former. Equation (6) may be put in a generalised form by writing it as follows :

$$N\left(\frac{4}{3}\pi H^3\right) = hV_w - \beta\phi_v \quad \dots (6a)$$

where β is a numerical factor which is to be found from experimental data.

For the chlorides of the cations mentioned in Table 1 it appears that at concentration 1 N and 25° the values of β is unity. Since β in equation (6a) is to be found from experimental data, equation (6a) and the others [(6) and (5)] which follow from it should be treated as semi-empirical.

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Interaction of Thallium(I) with Some Plant Auxins at Dropping Mercury Electrode

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3-INDOLEACETIC acid, 3-indolebutyric acid and 1-naphthaleneacetic acid are endogenous plant auxins which play multifarious role in the physiology of plants^{1,2}. No work has so far been reported on the polarographic determination of the stability constants of metal complexes with these plant auxins. In the present investigation, a study of the interaction of thallium(I) with these auxins at dropping mercury electrode in aqueous and aqueous-ethanol mixture media has, therefore, been undertaken.

Experimental

Reagents: Thallium(I) sulphate (B.D.H., AnalaR), 3-indoleacetic acid (E. Merck), 3-indolebutyric acid

(Loba Chemie), and 1-naphthaleneacetic acid (Sisco) were used as such. All other chemicals used were of guaranteed purity. Triple distilled mercury and double distilled water were used. Ethanol was dried successively over lime and anhydrous copper sulphate, and distilled over sodium. The distillate was treated with pure magnesium turnings and a little iodine, warmed under reflux to start the reaction and then allowed to stand till the reaction subsided. The contents were finally distilled at 78° at a take-off ratio of 1 : 5.

Solutions: Stock solution of thallium (0.02 M) was prepared in water and standardized³. The sodium salts of the ligands were prepared and pH of the solutions adjusted with sodium hydroxide using ELICO pH meter model LI-10. Solutions containing the metal ion ($4 \times 10^{-4} M$) and varying concentrations of the ligand in water, 10% and/or 50% ethanol were prepared at ionic strength 0.5 M maintained with sodium perchlorate.

Solutions of 3-indoleacetic acid, 3-indolebutyric acid and 1-naphthaleneacetic acid (0.004 M) in water, 10% and/or 50% ethanol at ionic strength 0.5 M , adjusted with sodium perchlorate, were titrated with carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution (0.1 M) at 15 ± 0.1 and/or 25 ± 0.1 °. After accounting for the dilution effect, the values of dissociation constant were calculated according to the method described by Albert and Serjeant⁴ (Table 1).

TABLE 1—pK VALUES OF VARIOUS PLANT AUXINS IN DIFFERENT MEDIA

Auxin	pK (± 0.03)	Temp. °C	Medium % Ethanol
3-Indoleacetic acid	3.75	25	0.00
	4.12	25	10
3-Indolebutyric acid	4.22	25	10
	3.52	25	10
1-Naphthaleneacetic acid	5.10	25	50
	3.61	15	10

The capillary characteristics measured in 0.1 M sodium perchlorate (open circuit) and at a mercury height (h) of 60 cm were $m = 2.113 \text{ mg sec}^{-1}$ and $t = 4.04 \text{ sec}$. Purified nitrogen, presaturated with the background solution to be polarographed, was used for deaeration. Electrolysis was carried out in a H-cell in conjunction with an agar-agar plug saturated with sodium chloride. An inert atmosphere was maintained over the solution during electrolysis. Polarograms of $4 \times 10^{-4} M$ thallium(I) solution were obtained in the presence of different concentrations of the ligand at pH 6.7 ± 0.1 and temperature at 15 ± 0.1 and/or 25 ± 0.1 ° using Radelkis polarograph type OH 102. An IR compensator was used while working with ethanolic solutions. The currents were corrected for the residual current. The resulting polarographic data as a function of ligand concentration which was calculated from the pH of the solution and the pK value of the auxin, are given in Table 2.

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NOTES

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF THALLIUM(I) IN THE PRESENCE OF CERTAIN PLANT AUXINS
 $Tl^+ = 0.4 \text{ mM}$; $\mu = 0.5 \text{ M (NaClO}_4\text{)}$; $pH = 6.7 \pm 0.1$

C_x	I		II		III		IV		V		VI	
	$E_{1/2}$	i_{d_s}/i_{d_c}										
	-V		-V		-V		-V		-V		-V	
0.00	0.4525	—	0.4425	—	0.4425	—	0.4425	—	0.4440	—	0.4430	—
0.02	0.4547	1.072	0.4462	1.115	0.4442	1.019	0.4447	1.044	0.4490	1.062	0.4455	1.040
0.05	0.4590	1.091	0.4511	1.145	0.4467	1.071	0.4465	1.076	0.4497	1.150	0.4470	1.059
0.10	0.4630	1.200	0.4575	1.176	0.4513	1.099	0.4502	1.123	0.4535	1.302	0.4497	1.139
0.15	0.4661	1.299	0.4623	1.261	0.4535	1.116	0.4512	1.178	0.4585	1.302	0.4537	1.154
0.20	0.4679	1.416	0.4675	1.299	0.4558	1.220	0.4557	1.161	0.4625	1.366	0.4565	1.154
0.25	0.4718	1.392	0.4687	1.426	0.4565	1.311	0.4568	1.239	0.4653	1.394	0.4592	1.259
0.30	0.4733	1.518	0.4718	1.475	0.4588	1.319	0.4587	1.304	0.4667	1.484	0.4595	1.333
0.35	0.4756	1.527	0.4731	1.522	0.4595	1.455	0.4595	1.397	0.4707	1.380	0.4610	1.452
0.40	0.4788	1.546	0.4735	1.706	0.4600	1.611	0.4610	1.431	0.4730	1.394	0.4617	1.462
0.45	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.4615	1.609	0.4725	1.643	0.4627	1.622
0.50	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.4635	1.630	0.4736	1.704	0.4642	1.667

- I Thallium(I)-3-indoleacetate in aqueous medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.
- II Thallium(I)-3-indoleacetate in 10% ethanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.
- III Thallium(I)-3-indolebutyrate in 10% ethanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.
- IV Thallium(I)-1-naphthaleneacetate in 10% ethanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.
- V Thallium(I)-1-naphthaleneacetate in 50% ethanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.
- VI Thallium(I)-1-naphthaleneacetate in 10% ethanol medium at $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The pK values of 3-indoleacetic acid, 3-indolebutyric acid and 1-naphthaleneacetic acid in 10% ethanol at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ are 4.12, 4.22 and 3.52, respectively. These values decrease in aqueous medium and increase on increasing the ethanol concentration or lowering the temperature.

Thallium(I) gives a single well-defined polarographic reduction wave in each solution. Current is directly proportional to $\sqrt{h_{eff}}$ showing that the reduction is diffusion-controlled. Plot of $E_{d,c}$ vs $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ is a straight line with a slope of 60 ± 2 mV. Cathodic reduction of thallium(I) in 3-indoleacetate, 3-indolebutyrate and 1-naphthaleneacetate is, therefore, reversible and involves one electron change. The decrease in diffusion current (i_d) and shift in the half-wave potential to more negative values as a function of the ligand concentration (C_x), suggest complex formation. The data is analysed using DeFord and Hume method⁶. Plots of $F_0([X])$ and $F_1([X])$ vs C_x give respectively straight lines with slope, and parallel to abscissa, in each case (Figs. 1 and 2) suggesting the formation of a single 1 : 1 complex. The values of the stability constants of thallium(I) complexes with these auxins are relatively low in aqueous medium, and

Fig. 1. Plot of $F_j([X])$ vs C_x at 25° .

- (a) Thallium(I)-3-indoleacetate in aqueous medium (—○—○—)
- (b) Thallium(I)-3-indoleacetate in 10% ethanol (—△—△—)
- (c) Thallium(I)-3-indolebutyrate in 10% ethanol (—□—□—)

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THALLIUM(I) COMPLEXES WITH SOME PLANT AUXINS

Sl. No.	Complex	Per cent ethanol	Temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	Stability constant β_1
1	Thallium(I)-3-indoleacetate	0.00	25 ± 0.1	8.05
2	Thallium(I)-3-indoleacetate	10.00	25 ± 0.1	11.82
3	Thallium(I)-3-indolebutyrate	10.00	25 ± 0.1	5.20
4	Thallium(I)-1-naphthaleneacetate	10.00	25 ± 0.1	4.88
5	Thallium(I)-1-naphthaleneacetate	50.00	25 ± 0.1	9.00
6	Thallium(I)-1-naphthaleneacetate	10.00	15 ± 0.1	5.30

increase on increasing the ethanol concentration or lowering temperature (Table 3). The temperature effect is, however, small as indicated by the values of the thermodynamic parameters for thallium-1-naphthaleneacetate complex ($\Delta F = -0.447 \text{ Kcal mole}^{-1}$, $\Delta H = -1.4172 \text{ Kcal mole}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S = 1.59 \text{ cal mole}^{-1} \text{ deg}^{-1}$). The low value of stability constant of thallium(I)-3-indolebutyrate complex may be due to the presence of more methylene groups in the chain having carboxylic group.

Fig. 2. Plot of $F_j([X])$ vs C_x for thallium(I)-1-naphthaleneacetate system in

- (a) 10% Ethanol at 25° (—○—○—)
- (b) 50% Ethanol at 25° (—□—□—)
- (c) 10% Ethanol at 15° (—△—△—)

Fig. 3. Plot of percentage distribution of thallium in various forms vs $-\log C_x$ at 25°

- (a) Thallium(I)-3-indoleacetate in aqueous medium (—○—○—)
- (b) Thallium(I)-3-indoleacetate in 10% ethanol (—△—△—)
- (c) Thallium(I)-3-indolebutyrate in 10% ethanol (—□—□—)

Percentage distribution of thallium in various forms as a function of ligand concentration is calculated and the values are presented in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 4. Plot of percentage distribution of thallium in various forms vs $-\log C_x$ for thallium(I)-1-naphthalene in

- (a) 10% Ethanol at 25° (—○—○—)
- (b) 50% Ethanol at 25° (—△—△—)
- (c) 10% Ethanol at 15° (—□—□—)

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some New 4-Ylidenetetronic Acid Derivatives*

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THE tetronic acid ring system constitutes important structural features in a wide range of biologically important natural products e.g., vitamin C and cardenolide digitoxigenin. The ring system is a characteristic structural feature in the 'pulvinic

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